

Data and service practices of Climate Service providers

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

1 Introduction and purpose

The goal of this survey is to gather data, software, and service practices from climate service providers to inform the formulation of useful and consistent guidelines for data, software, and services used and developed by Climate Services as part of the [Climateurope2 project](#) - Work Package 2. The answers will help us to improve the [preliminary guidelines](#).

The survey is composed of sections along the stages of a climate service provision plus introductory questions about your Climate Service and concluded with questions about the organization's standards/certificates:

- 2 Information on your role and your Climate Service
- 3 Data Source
- 4 Data Processing
- 5 Data and Information Product Sharing and Communication
- 6 Organization Practices and Transparency

The thematic sections contain, among others, questions about good and bad examples you would like to share as well as a questions on requirements for more standardization. Many questions are optional, because we do not expect you to answer every question but those you can share information on. Depending on the provided level of detail, the completion of the survey will require 5-20 min.

Climateurope2 uses [IPCC's definition for Climate Services](#): "Climate services involve the provision of climate information in such a way as to assist decision-making. The service includes appropriate engagement from users and providers, is based on scientifically credible information and expertise, has an effective access mechanism and responds to user needs."

Thank you very much for spending some time sharing your knowledge and experience with us!

2 Information on your role and your Climate Service

- * 2.1 What is your role in your organization?

- (Project) Manager
- Consultant
- Data Scientist
- Scientist
- IT Expert
- ...other

2.2 If you have answered "other", please specify your roles:

*2.3 How many years have you been working as a Climate Service provider?

- < 2 years
- 2 - 5 years
- 5 - 10 years
- > 10 years

*2.4 Sector category information:

- Government
- International Organization
- Media
- NGOs & Associations
- Policy & Public Institutions
- Private sector
- Public sector
- Research & Academia
- ...other

2.5 If you have answered "other", please name your sector(s):

*2.6 Please provide a short description of your Climate Service:

*2.7 Who are your customers/users?

- scientists
- general public
- public authorities
- private companies
- ...other

2.8 If you have answered "other", please specify your customers/users:

2.9 Is there anything else you want us to know about your expertise or your Climate Service?

3 Data Source

Climate Services rely on data or information. We are interested in data standards and data access.

* 3.1 Which data sources do you use for your Climate Service?

- in-house data sources
- external data sources
- both

* 3.2 Source data from which data providers do you use?

Thinking of your experience with source data. Do you want to share a good and/or bad experience?

3.3 ...good experience:

3.4 ...bad experience:

* 3.5 In which data formats is the source data provided?

- NetCDF
- CSV
- PDF
- Shapefile
- geoTiff
- grib
- KML
- HDF
- JSON
- Zarr
- ...other

3.6 If you have answered "other", please specify the data formats:

3.7 Does the data comply with additional community standards?

(An example is the [Climate and Forecast standard for NetCDF](#))

*3.8 Are there license or access/usage restrictions for the source data?

- Yes
- For some
- No

3.9 If you have answered "yes" or "for some", please describe the restrictions you encounter:

*3.10 How do you access the data?

- copy/access from in-house storage
- general webpage
- portal or web application like an Atlas
- API access
- direct download from server or cloud storage
- ...other

3.11 If you have answered "other", please specify your data access:

3.12 How easy to use is the source data for you in terms of the [FAIR \(Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable\)](#) data principles and data quality...

(1 star = low/bad, 5 star = high/good)

...findability	
...accessibility	
...interoperability	
...reusability	
...data quality	

3.13 Do you want to share the reasons behind your rating?

3.14 How important are standards for...

	unimportant	somewhat unimportant	neutral	somewhat important	important
* ...data formats	<input type="radio"/>				
* ...naming conventions and controlled vocabularies	<input type="radio"/>				
* ...machine-accessibility of data	<input type="radio"/>				
* ...machine-accessibility of metadata and documentations	<input type="radio"/>				
* ...data licenses	<input type="radio"/>				

3.15 Are there other standards required or desirable around source data?

4 Data Processing

We understand data processing as the transformation of source data or information into a Climate Service product. We want to understand practices of software and digital service development applied by Climate Service providers.

* 4.1 Do you develop software in-house or use external software?

- no software used
- in-house software development
- external software usage
- in-house and external software usage

4.2 What do you use the software for in your Climate Service?

Thinking of your experience with data processing to derive your Climate Service products: Do you want to share a good and/or bad experience?

4.3 ...good experience:

4.4 ...bad experience:

4.5 Which digital services do you provide (if any)?

* 4.6 Which programming languages do you use in your Climate Service e.g. for data processing, visualization and/or digital service provision?

- not applicable or unknown
- Python
- C/C++
- Fortran
- Java/Javascript

- Ruby
- R
- SQL
- ...other

4.7 If you have answered "other", please specify the programming languages you use:

4.8 Do you use software tools and/or packages, e.g. a GIS application?

* 4.9 Do you apply AI/machine-learning?

- not applicable or unknown
- Yes
- No
- Not yet, but planned

* 4.10 Which criteria or guidelines/best practices do you apply for software and service development in your organization?

- not applicable or unknown
- Open Source software usage
- Open Source software sharing
- software versioning
- code review
- CI/CD (continuous integration and continuous delivery)
- software and service security (ISO/EC 27000)
- software quality (ISO/EC 25000)
- ...other

4.11 If you have answered "other", please specify your organization's additional guidelines for software development:

4.12 How do you rate your software and digital services in regard to...

(1 star = low/bad, 5 star = high/good)

...software maturity	
...services maturity	
...transparency of applied methods	

...documentation of software and services	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
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4.13 Do you want to share the reasons behind your rating?

4.14 How important do you regard guidelines on...

	unimportant	somewhat unimportant	neutral	somewhat important	important
* ...software versioning	<input type="radio"/>				
* ...security	<input type="radio"/>				
* ...ethics, e.g. for AI usage	<input type="radio"/>				
*software licenses	<input type="radio"/>				

4.15 Are there other guidelines for software and service development and application required or desirable?

5 Data and Information Product Sharing and Communication

We want to understand what Climate Service products you provide, which best practices you apply and how you interact with your customers/users.

* 5.1 What kind of Climate Service products do you provide?

- data products
- code
- service application
- expert reports for customers
- ...other

5.2 If you have answered "other", please specify your organization's additional Climate Service products:

* 5.3 How can the customer/user access your Climate Service products?

- product like a report is sent to the customer
- online download from Climate Service website
- online GUI like an Atlas
- online machine-access like an API

- shared upon request
- ...other

5.4 If you have answered "other", please specify how you share your Climate Service products:

Thinking of your Climate Service products: Do you want to share a good and/or bad example out of your experience?

5.5 ...good experience:

5.6 ...bad experience:

* 5.7 In which data formats is the data and information products provided?

- NetCDF
- CSV
- PDF
- Shapefile
- geoTiff
- grib
- KML
- HDF
- JSON
- Zarr
- ...other

5.8 If you have answered "other", please specify the data and/or information formats:

5.9 Does your Climate Service product comply to additional community standards?

(An example is the Climate and Forecast standard for NetCDF)

* 5.10 How do you support your customers/users in using your Climate Service products?

- documentation
- tutorials/workshops/webinars
- ticketing system

- notifications e.g. about software or data updates
- regular customer/user feedback
- ...other

5.11 If you have answered "other", please specify further ways of customer/user support:

5.12 How would you rate your Climate Service product in regard to...

(1 star = low/bad, 5 star = high/good)

compliance to standards	
easy-to-use / easy-to-understand	
maturity	
customer/user engagement	
product development and versioning	

5.13 According to your experience, how important are guidelines and standards for Climate Service products in regard to...

	unimportant	somewhat unimportant	neutral	somewhat important	important
* ...data formats	<input type="radio"/>				
* ...data or information versioning	<input type="radio"/>				
* ...data and information sharing	<input type="radio"/>				
*machine-accessibility and -readability	<input type="radio"/>				
* ...data/software licenses	<input type="radio"/>				
* ...naming conventions and controlled vocabularies	<input type="radio"/>				

5.14 Are there other guidelines for Climate Service products and sharing required or desirable?

6 Organizational Practices and Transparency

A Climate Service product and its quality and sustainability is closely related to organizational commitments. We would like to learn about these commitments/best practices/certifications.

* 6.1 Does your organization have a guideline or certificate on its general operations?

- no guidelines or certificates
- in-house guidelines
- published guidelines
- [CoreTrustSeal](#) certificate (data preservation self-assessment)
- [ISO 9001](#) Quality Management certificate
- ...other

6.2 If you have answered "other", please specify the guidelines or certificates of your organization:

Thinking of your experience with the development of guidelines/certificates and their usefulness: Do you want to share a good and/or bad experience?

6.3 ...good experience:

6.4 ...bad experience:

6.5 What is your main motivation for organizational guidelines or the application for certificates?

6.6 How important are for your organization...

(1 star = unimportant, 5 star = very important)

Certificates	
Transparency of operations	
Reliability of services	
Sustainability of services	

6.7 Do you want to share the reasons behind your rating?

7 Final Remarks / Join the CE2 Network

7.1 Do you want to share anything else we missed out? Additional standards and/or good practices, standardization requirements, or anything else?

7.2 May CE2 contact you about your answers? If yes, please provide your email address.

(This contact will only be used for this survey. It will not be shared outside of the WP2 Task 1 members and deleted after the finalization of the survey.)

7.3 Do you want to **join the CE2 network** to receive regular updates from the project and be included in related future projects?

(At the end of the project, the repository will become property of the European Commission, who will decide on its operations, archival, and reuse — especially whether further updates to its content will be allowed — thereby fostering sustainability and continued relevance to the community.)

Yes

* 7.4 First Name

* 7.5 Last Name

* 7.6 Email

* 7.7 Country: EU member state

- | | | | |
|-------------------------------------|------------------------------------|--|--|
| <input type="radio"/> Austria (AT) | <input type="radio"/> Estonia (EE) | <input type="radio"/> Italy (IT) | <input type="radio"/> Portugal (PT) |
| <input type="radio"/> Belgium (BE) | <input type="radio"/> Finland (FI) | <input type="radio"/> Latvia (LV) | <input type="radio"/> Romania (RO) |
| <input type="radio"/> Bulgaria (BG) | <input type="radio"/> France (FR) | <input type="radio"/> Lithuania (LT) | <input type="radio"/> Slovak Republic (SK) |
| <input type="radio"/> Croatia (HR) | <input type="radio"/> Germany (DE) | <input type="radio"/> Luxembourg (LU) | <input type="radio"/> Slovenia (SI) |
| <input type="radio"/> Cyprus (CY) | <input type="radio"/> Greece (EL) | <input type="radio"/> Malta (MT) | <input type="radio"/> Spain (ES) |
| <input type="radio"/> Czechia (CZ) | <input type="radio"/> Hungary (HU) | <input type="radio"/> Netherlands (NL) | <input type="radio"/> Sweden (SE) |
| <input type="radio"/> Denmark (DK) | <input type="radio"/> Ireland (IE) | <input type="radio"/> Poland (PL) | <input type="radio"/> ...other (ID315) |

7.8 Please provide non-EU country:

* 7.9 City:

* 7.10 Gender:

- Male
- Female
- Other
- Prefer not to answer

* 7.11 Position:

* 7.12 Organization:

* 7.13 Sector category information:

- Government
- International Organization
- Media
- NGOs & Associations
- Policy & Public Institutions
- Private sector
- Public sector
- Research & Academia

By submitting the form, any provided personal data will be processed for the legitimate and necessary purposes described in the below information form. Please indicate your consent for the following purposes:

I agree to the dissemination of the materials collected as part of the activity's objectives.

I agree to the dissemination of the materials collected as part of the activity's objectives, and to being contacted to receive updates, results and announcements, and to take part in other research activities (e.g. surveys, interviews), including those unrelated to the current activity.

I agree to both the purposes above mentioned and to processing of my personal data for future contact and research studies outside the scope of this project.

[Privacy Policy information form CE2 WP2 1 survey.pdf](#)

Thanks a lot!

Martina Stockhause (German Climate Computing Center, DKRZ) on behalf of Climateurope2 WP2 Task 1